

Impact of pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) on the risk of bacterial sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among cisgender women: a systematic review

Search strategy

We will search databases for the concepts of: (1) HIV, (2) PrEP and (3) STIs and (4) women, reported in the latest articles and conference abstracts published – see Table below.

Adapted from Werner *et al*¹ developed with a librarian and a researcher based at Imperial College London.

Ovid Database search

MEDLINE/EMBASE

	Search terms (including MeSH)
1	exp HIV infections/
2	exp HIV/
3	(hiv OR hiv1 OR hiv2 OR human immun* deficiency virus*).ab,ti,kw.
4	1 or 2 or 3
5	exp Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis/
6	PrEP.ab,ti,kw
7	((Preexposure OR Pre exposure) AND (prophylaxis OR chemoprophylaxis OR chemoprevention OR prevention)).ab,ti,kw.
8	Truvada OR tenofovir OR emtricitabine OR tenofovir disoproxil fumarate.ab,ti,kw.
9	5 or 6 or 7 or 8
10	exp Sexually Transmitted Diseases/
11	exp Sexually Transmitted Diseases, Bacterial/
12	(sexually transmitted infection* or sexually transmitted disease* or bacterial sexually transmitted infection* or syphilis or gonorrh?ea or chlamydia* or venereal disease*).ab,ti,kw.
13	10 or 11 or 12
14	exp Women/
15	exp Mother/
16	(wom#n OR female* OR mother*).ab,ti,kw.
17	14 or 15 or 16
18	4 and 9 and 13 and 17

Web of Science search

	Search terms
1	(hiv or hiv1 or hiv2 or human immun* deficiency virus)
2	(PrEP or Truvada OR TDF OR tenofovir OR emtricitabine or (Preexposure or Pre exposure) AND (prophylaxis or chemoprophylaxis or chemoprevention or prevention))
3	(sexually transmitted infection* or sexually transmitted disease* or bacterial sexually transmitted infection* or syphilis or gonorrh?ea or chlamydia* or venereal disease*)
4	(wom\$n OR female* OR mother*)
5	#1 and #2 and #3 and #4

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Cochrane CENTRAL

	Search terms (including MeSH)
#1	MeSH descriptor: [HIV Infections] explode all trees
#2	MeSH descriptor: [HIV] explode all trees
#3	hiv:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#4	#1 or #2 or #3
#5	MeSH descriptor: [Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis] explode all trees
#6	MeSH descriptor: [Emtricitabine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate Drug Combination] explode all trees
#7	Pre-exposure prophylaxis:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#8	truvada:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#9	#5 or #6 or #7 or #8
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Sexually Transmitted Diseases] explode all trees
#11	MeSH descriptor: [Sexually Transmitted Diseases, Bacterial] explode all trees
#12	sexually transmitted infection*:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#13	sexually transmitted disease*:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#14	syphilis:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#15	gonorrh?ea:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#16	chlamydia*:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#17	#10 or #11 or #12 or #13 or #14 or #15 or #16
#18	MeSH descriptor: [Women] explode all trees
#19	MeSH descriptor: [Mothers] explode all trees
#20	wom?n:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#21	female:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#22	mother:ab,ti,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#23	#18 or #19 or #20 or #21 or #22
#24	#4 and #9 and #17 and #23

References

1. Werner RN, Gaskins M, Nast A, et al. Incidence of sexually transmitted infections in men who have sex with men and who are at substantial risk of HIV infection – A meta-analysis of data from trials and observational studies of HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis. *PLOS ONE* 2018;13:1-24. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0208107